

An SRI based approach to increase building smartness

Mr. Konstantinos Tsatsakis

R&D Manager

Mr. Giorgos Papadopoulos

R&D Manager

Contact details of corresponding author

Tel: + 357 2535 5585

E-mail: kostas@suite5.eu

Address: Alexandreias 2, Bridge Tower 3013, Limassol, Cyprus

ABSTRACT

The EU has committed to reduce by at least 40% greenhouse gas emission by 2030 through the so called “Clean energy for all Europeans package” [1] which set the necessary legal framework and financial infrastructure to achieve this ambitious goal. On the other hand, the most recent Green Deal aim to transform the EU into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy, ensuring no net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050. Towards this direction, the EU commission has promoted the establishment of a Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) [2][5] for buildings to provide information on the technological readiness of buildings for interacting with their occupants and the energy grids, and their capabilities for more efficient operation and better performance through ICT technologies in the form of services.

In this paper we present a holistic building energy management framework targeting to increase the SRI [3][4] level of the buildings by introducing different types of services targeting SRI uptake and thus changing the role of buildings from unorganised energy consumers to active agents orchestrating and optimising their energy consumption, production and storage, with the goal of increasing energy performance, maximising occupants' benefit, and facilitating grid operation. Such smart capabilities can effectively assist in creating healthier and more comfortable buildings with lower energy consumption and lower carbon footprint. The technological framework is complemented by suitable business models and exploitation strategies to target the broad market of smart building. In section 2, the overall architecture of the proposed SRI based framework is presented. Then, in Section 3, the focus is about the delivery of non-energy services as a core parameter of the SRI methodology. Last but not least, the business model's definition is complementing the work in Section 4 in order to pave the way for further exploitation of the different services.

A HOLISTIC SRI BASED BUILDING ENERGY MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

At first, the details of the innovative building management framework which brings together a wide range of SRI oriented technologies and integrates them in a holistic and interoperable framework are presented with the focus on the different operational layers that consist of the holistic solution. The analysis of the architecture remains at a functional level, specifying the detailed functionalities to be served by the different software components as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Conceptual architecture for the SRI oriented building management framework

The different layers that comprise the integrated framework are briefly described below considering also the different modules of functionality as defined in the schema. As depicted above there are the core layers of the architecture and the additional business and asset layer that complement the overall picture. Starting with the latter:

The **Business layer** represents the point of views and the interactions with the end-users (e.g., building users/managers) and stakeholders (e.g., ESCO, Aggregators, etc). This layer provides the technical and business aspects of the large-scale pilots and associated requirements, with a specific focus on the “reference” nature of the envisaged architecture. This layer also enables to create also holistic links among different business models.

On the other hand, the **Asset layer** consists of heterogeneous legacy equipment and systems already deployed in the buildings that must be integrated and managed intelligently by the proposed framework.

Namely:

- Short-life appliances (e.g., fridges, ovens, washing machines, microwaves, etc).
- Long-life appliances (e.g., HVAC, boilers, radiators, DHW (domestic hot water) devices, ventilation, lighting, etc.).
- Energy building equipment (e.g., renewable sources, energy storage, e-vehicle recharging points, energy demanding points, smart meters, smart actuators, etc).
- Management systems (e.g., EMSs) already deployed in existing buildings to monitor and control legacy equipment.

These devices that exist in building can be categorised in four families: Envelope Adaptation systems (e.g., windows automatic opening and shading), Technical Building Systems (HVAC, DHW, built-in lighting, building automation and control, on-site electricity generation), Indoor and Outdoor Information Systems (i.e., sensors) and Entertainment Systems (e.g., television, radio, etc.).

It is evident from the schema above, that there are three key layers (Integration, Knowledge, Function) that define the ICT software details of the solution with the other two layers (Asset & Business Layer) to complement the overall picture for the end-to-end demonstration of the proposed framework. The details of these technical layers are provided following a bottom-up approach.

The **Integration layer** stand on top of the asset layer and provides the mechanisms for the remote control and data monitoring from different building equipment, systems and external data sources (i.e., weather predictions) with heterogeneous protocols and technologies. This counts for (a) **IoT Gateways and Smart Controllers** to bridge the gap between smart home devices and the core data brokering by translating legacy protocols (e.g. Modbus, Zigbee, etc) of digital equipment to standardised Internet protocol in order to monitor and control their operations, (b) **building management systems integrators** to handle the same

functionality in commercial buildings where BMS systems are available (c) **external data source wrappers** to incorporate energy (e.g. energy tariffs) and weather related data from national or international organizations into the common management framework.

This layer will be also responsible for the homogenisation of the communication protocols through a real time broker and further storage to different data formats to enable the easy link between the physical assets and the layers of knowledge and function that follow. More specifically, the role of the **Real-Time Data Broker** is to receive continuous updates about the building's state and to make sure that updated information reaches the intended parties. It does so by providing querying capabilities as well as subscription mechanisms by which interested parties will receive notifications according to their data requirements. The Real-Time Data Broker, follows the NGS-LD standard, based in the JSON-LD data format, to allow representing semantic information, further enhancing the context representation. Related to the latter, all SRI principles are incorporated in the common information model in order to further enable the provision of added value SRI oriented services.

Last but not least, the **Platform Data Repository** is defined to act as the mid-term data storage for temporal series of data. Its mission is to record context information changes (for example building sensor readings) as they happen. It does so by leveraging the subscription mechanism of the Real-Time Data Broker, which will result in a stream of notifications of data entity changes from the broker, which the Platform Data Repository will store in its internal database.

On top of the Integration layer, the **Knowledge Layer** enables the provision of modular tools for creating building knowledge, based on homogenised data through data processing and analytics to upgrade the smartness of the buildings. At a first level, annotations to the integrated data are defined in order to build a background **Knowledge Graph (KG)** that facilitates the extraction of the SRI information along with relevant information about preferences related to user behaviours. A state-of-the-art ontological based

module is defined to serve the SRI calculation on the basis of the data coming from different sources (sensors, appliances descriptions, user profiles, etc) by means of mapping and modeling tools.

In addition, we incorporate in the proposed framework artificial intelligence data algorithms (e.g., machine learning and deep learning) to enable self-learning capacities and automatic decisions to improve energy savings and the overall performance of buildings. Moreover, the data algorithms will generate valuable knowledge to feed the upper layer of smart services. More specifically, the **User-centric services Analytics Engine** will actively contribute to the extraction of user-centric profiles and comfort-profile preferences. Additionally, energy descriptive and predictive analytics will be provided, in order to deliver useful behavioural insights to the building occupant, regarding his indoor environment for better awareness and assurance of optimal indoor conditions. Complementary to this, a **Grid-centric services Analytics Engine** is incorporated in the platform in order to provide energy related analytics to serve mainly grid related functionalities. State of the art generation and demand forecasting analytics will be extracted that will be further complemented by flexibility related analytics in order to provide added value information to the different services that will serve the grid related functionalities of the building.

On top of the proposed ICT framework is the **Function layer** which includes multiple smart cost-effective services offered to the end users in order to optimize the energy saving, the occupants' satisfaction, the overall performance of the buildings and the grid operations as the three interlinked principles of SRI. More specifically, the proposed framework is focusing at the provision of different layers of services to the building occupants:

- Starting with the energy efficiency related services, the **Self-Consumption Optimization Engine** is responsible to provide energy savings optimization (towards the energy utility operators as well as the building occupants) through the day-ahead forecasting of energy generation, energy storage and energy consumption at building level. It is evident that this module is able to address the savings

needs of the simplest demand only case while also incorporating additional DERs (PV, EV, battery) in the energy savings optimization process.

- Complementary to this, the role of the **Predictive Maintenance Engine** is to enable the provision of equipment maintenance related services, also a key aspect highlighted in the Smart Readiness Indicator methodology. By applying state of the art machine learning techniques over the data streams, the scope of this module is to enable the extraction of useful outlier insights related to the performance of the equipment in building premises.
- At the 2nd layer of SRI, the role of the **Comfort, Convenience and Wellbeing Engine** is to enable the provision of non-energy services to the building occupants as a key aspect highlighted in the Smart Readiness Indicator methodology. On the basis of user and social driven requirements defined through the analysis at the building premises, the scope of this component is to first enable identification of poor indoor conditions in buildings that may cause comfort or health issues to the building occupants. Furthermore, the component incorporates smart services that will enable either automated control of the building devices to ensure comfort, health and well-being conditions or context based personalized notifications and messages to building occupants related to the comfort and well-being conditions in premises.
- The **Demand Flexibility Management Engine** covers the needs of the 3rd layer of the SRI towards the provision of flexibility related services to the grid. The role of this module is to enable flexibility calculation and further the delivery of the appropriate interfaces in order to ensure the prompt exploitation of the available flexibility by 3rd party business entities.
- Complementary to the aforementioned SRI business-oriented services, there are additional modules defined in order to address the list of 7 impact criteria of the SRI. Information to building occupants is a very important parameter of the SRI and thus the **Building Occupants Visualization Dashboard** is defined to serve as the user-centric reporting tool of the proposed framework. As a basis, this tool will incorporate the visualization of the historic, aggregated and real-time data context from metering and sensing of smart devices across the entire topology landscape. All the

descriptive and predictive analytics results mentioned in previous sections will also be visualized in the dashboard. On top of these features, new innovations will be added in the overall functionality such as the real time visualization of EPC/SRI certificate, information that is extracted through calculation performed by the **SRI/ EPC Evaluation Engine**. This is actually one of the most innovative aspects as the SRI performance will not be extracted through the static methodology defined by the guidelines; rather actual premises data will be considered for the actual calculation of the smartness of the building.

- Last but not least and in order to server the business validation of the proposed framework, an extra module is defined, named as **Smart Contracts Management Engine**. The role of this module is to enable handling contractual process in real time, and thus delivering the dynamic pricing framework required for the applicability of innovative business models that envisioned in energy sector.

We have to point out that there exists an extra layer, the Protection Layer, which provides the techniques and protocols to ensure the security, privacy and trust of the data exchange in all the horizontal layers. Due to the interoperable and connected nature of the proposed framework, security, privacy and trust mechanisms are required to protect the data exchange among physical assets, integration agents, knowledge processing techniques, smart services and user interfaces in all abovementioned layers. The details of these security/privacy mechanisms, to be developed based on FIWARE Security Enablers to allow devices/systems authentication, privacy preserving & data protection, services access control and user management are not part of this paper.

The different layers of the proposed building management framework were presented above. While there are many functionalities provided by the different components, the focus of the paper is on the details of the Comfort, Convenience and Wellbeing services which is a critical and important aspect of the Smart Readiness Indicator methodology.

SMART COMFORT, CONVENIENCE AND WELLBEING SERVICES TO SUPPORT BUILDING SMARTNESS

The scope of this section is to provide the details for the proposed Comfort, Convenience and Wellbeing services delivered as part of the holistic building management framework. As stated above the role of this service bundle is to first enable identification of poor indoor conditions in buildings that may cause comfort or health issues to the building occupants. Furthermore, the module incorporates smart services that will enable either automated control of the building devices to ensure comfort, health and well-being conditions or context based personalized notifications and messages to building occupants related to the comfort and well-being conditions in premises (while keeping the energy usage as low as possible to meet the requirements). In order to properly design well fitted services, the review of the most recent regulation in the field is required.

Starting with thermal comfort evaluation, ASHRAE Standard 55 [6] is the document that defines the KPIs with focus on PMV and PPD. In addition to these KPIs, adaptive comfort models are incorporated in the standard. At EU level the most recent standard is the EN 16789-1 (which updated the well know EN 15251) where thermal comfort KPIs are defined. We have to point out that relevant KPIs [8] are imported also in the certification bodies such LEED, WELL etc... to address thermal comfort evaluating needs. Considering visual comfort evaluation, it encompasses a variety of aspects, such as aesthetic quality, lighting ambiance and view: Light quality, Luminosity, Absence of glare. As stated in [7] and the EN 16789-1 standard, specific metrics are related to health aspects, as also highlighted in the SRI methodology.

In addition to comfort related parameters, health related parameters need to be considered in the analysis. Focusing on specific IAQ values that are monitored from smart systems, there is the existing regulation that clearly specifies the calculation methodology and the boundary values. An overview of this information is available in [10]. The threshold values as specified in the EPA regulation for the most common IAQ values monitored in the residential building environment along with the calculation formulas are:

- PM2.5: PM2.5, in particular, are particles which are 2.5 µm or less in diameter. Their threshold limit value is 25 µg/m³, based on 24-hour data.
- CO₂: Human health effects can be observed at levels over 7,000 ppm. Therefore, the occupational limits set are 5,000 ppm TLV-TWA* and 30,000 ppm TLV-STEL**.
- NO₂: Due to the adverse effects associated with nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), the EPA strengthened its health guidelines and set a 1-hour standard at the level of 100 ppb.
- tVOC: As it combines the values from different VOCs. Note that its threshold limit value is 0.1 ppm TLV-TWA* and 0.3 ppm TLV-STEL**.

**TLV-TWA: Threshold Limit Value - Time Weighted Average (usually 8 hours)*

***TLV-STEL: Threshold Limit Value - Short Term Exposure Limit (usually 15 minutes)*

Related to health and IAQ conditions, there is a high interest especially in the COVID-19 era. This is clearly depicted also in EU reporting where there is a clear linkage of air quality conditions with COVID-19[9]. Also, all major health bodies define IAQ related measures and processes in order to reduce the potential for airborne transmission of COVID-19 in building environment [5-9]. In [11]the positive connection between air pollutants (PM_{2.5} and NO₂) and COVID-19 contagion urges to level the air quality index. From the viewpoint of engineering controls, ventilation can help dilute contaminants and reduce infection risk. As suggested, air should not be recirculated, and thus hygiene ventilation can be done using 100% fresh air with efficient energy consumption for sustainability[12]. Even at commercial level, there are solutions that combine metrics from sensors in order to identify the risk of potential for airborne transmission of COVID-19 [13]. It is evident from aforementioned analysis that employing preventive measures to mitigate air pollution can reduce exposure rate of COVID-19 and thus the design of non-energy services should target also this new situation.

Considering long term impact there exist some literature that estimates the impact of smart building systems and services in non-energy related aspects. While this long-term impact analysis is out of the scope of this

paper and the proposed framework, the review of the work is provided as reference. JRC [14] reports a synthesis of co-benefit impacts from many studies but the most significant is the so-called COMBI study (Calculating and Operationalising the Multiple Benefits of Energy Efficiency in Europe), which compiled an assessment of health and wellbeing impacts from all 28 EU countries and derived monetized benefits for: asthma (DALY), excess winter mortality, indoor air pollution, mortality - ozone, mortality -PM2.5, reduced congestion amongst others. The JRC study compiles and synthesizes the data on the impacts and monetised values of the following:

- reduced winter mortality attributable to lower ozone and PM2.5
- reduced winter morbidity attributable to lower indoor air pollution (units of 1000 YOLL), lower asthma (units of DALY), lower PM2.5 (units of YOLL)
- reduced diseases arising from thermal discomfort
- learning and productivity benefits due to better concentration, savings/higher productivity due to avoided “sick building syndrome” whose value can then be assessed in terms of active days gained (indoor exposure) and workforce performance (mn workdays).

Furthermore, a survey from 2015 and 2016 examined several characteristics of a healthy home and the importance for healthy living. In this context, participants were asked to score health categories from 1 to 7 (1 being “not important” and 7 being “very important”). The results of this survey indicate:

- sleeping well received a score of 6.4
- ventilation for fresh air scored 6.1
- plenty of daylight received a score of 5.9.

In this context, smart building technologies can help occupants to achieve the characteristics of healthy homes, by increasing the level of controllability/automatization with the use of indoor environmental quality sensors (to regulate temperature, humidity, ventilation, lighting and CO2) and maintain healthy

indoor climate conditions and thermal comfort level. This is the approach adopted for the services envisioned at the proposed framework, presented in the following figure.

Figure 2 Non-Energy Services for the building environment

More specifically there are 3 layers that comprise the data driven service framework, namely:

- **Comfort, Health and Well Being Interface Layer:** The role of this module is to act as the wrapper of the application in order to ensure information exchange with external components. The role of this bundle is twofold: (a) to ensure integration with external systems in order to retrieve data from the building environment (as specified above) required for the provision of the non-energy services and (b) to perform a real-time evaluation of comfort, health and well-being aspects considering also the KPI values as specified in the state-of-the-art analysis presented above.
- **Comfort, Health and Wellbeing Recommendation Engine:** The role of this DSS module is to correlate building contextual conditions along with the extracted comfort profiles and user settings in order to generate the appropriate notifications associated with the indoor conditions in premises. More specifically, the features of the recommendation approach (via a tailor-made and personalized recommendation engine) should include:

- Timely and Context-Aware: triggers and meaningful feedback for timely need-to-act will be offered close to relevant events and necessary actions, taking into account real-time conditions like environmental conditions from sensors (luminance, temperature & humidity)
- Non-intrusive: feedback modality, frequency and context will be configurable to ensure discreteness
- Personalized: feedback will be customized to occupant characteristics and relevant energy behaviours, comfort preferences and contextual requirements. Feedback from the end users is also considered in order to ensure personalization at the different notifications triggered to the users.

The high-level overview of the recommendation engine is presented in the following figure.

Figure 3 Non-Energy Services Recommendation Engine

- **Comfort, Health and Well Being Automation Engine:** The role of this DSS module is to correlate building contextual conditions along with the extracted comfort profiles and user settings in order to automatize the operation of controllable devices (focus on HVAC, Lights etc.) on the way to ensure the establishment of a comfortable, health and well-conditioned environment. By taking into account impact criteria such as the goal objective (comfort vs health), the level of automation (frequency of triggers) and the feedback from the end users (by rating the automation actions performed by the system), the DSS system adapts its operation in order

to perform the appropriate control strategies. A high-level overview of the DSS system is presented in the following figure.

Figure 4 Non-Energy Services Automation Engine

TEST ACTIVITIES & BUSINESS MODELS

The overall solution and integrated optimization framework will be demonstrated and validated until 2023 in four different regions around Europe. In Spain, the pilot site is located at Region de Murcia and includes two different types of building, an office building and a residential building. The demonstration activities for the office building will take place at CEEIC in Cartagena. This business incubator building focus on start-up and early-stage innovative companies. 20 spaces between company's offices and lecture rooms will participate in the validation activities for the proposed framework. The residential building selected is located at the city centre of Murcia. Four apartments will be involved in the pilot site. Each apartment is approximately 125 square meters and they are equipped with common domestic appliances. In Greece, a residential building complex at the region of Thessaloniki is considered as part of the demonstration activities. Similar to the previous case, typical domestic appliances are placed in the region and the only smart devices already installed are smart thermostats that control the refrigerant flow that serve the fan coils to perform the conditioning of the apartments. The Swedish pilot site is located in Skellefteå, a city in northern Sweden. The pilot site includes a building which is both residential and commercial. It has 12 apartments and a commercial space at the front of the building on the ground floor. The total area including

the commercial space is 1920 square meters of heated area and 1278 square meters of living area. The occupant age group ranges between 20-76 years with average age of 50 years approximately. Last but not least the Irish demo site is formed by commercial and residential buildings, having a large wealth of data which is locked at the moment on closed systems that need to be integrated. The commercial pilot building is the National Centre for the Circular Economy in Ireland, the Rediscovery Centre. The building is a repurposed boiler house and includes solar PV, CHP, heat pump and solar thermal. The sensors and actuators are connected to a Building Management System that allows control of services. It is an ideal demonstration site for optimisation in a building with a BEMS and a range of energy using and conversion technologies. In addition, two privately owned residential buildings located within a Sustainable Energy Community located to the south east of Dublin City have been chosen as good exemplars of smart upgrades for energy and related services.

Figure 5 Demonstration Sites for framework evaluation

In all these demo sites different types of services as presented above will be tested taking into account the data gathered from the installations in premises. Based on pilot business needs the focus should be on the delivery of SRI oriented services spanning from energy savings and self-consumption optimization, comfort and health maximization while also considering the potential integration of the buildings to the grid towards the provision of flexibility related services.

The demonstration activities should be accompanied by the definition of profitable business models as the main interest for the consumers and business stakeholders is to ensure financial profit along with any other social impact. The future of EEB (Energy Efficiency Building) sector involves engaged all relevant stakeholders becoming active producer of data, rather than passive consumers of data provided by other parties. The combination of the data collection, data analysis, and the use of AI allow exploiting the real potential of smart buildings, which in addition ensure the provision of new services to occupants, managers and the grid. The deregulation of the energy market and furthermore the incorporation of buildings in market-based frameworks as defined in the electricity sector will enable the definition of innovative fine grained business schemas that will fully remunerate the smartness potential of the buildings.

CONCLUSIONS & SUMMARY

At present, about 45% of the EU's buildings are over 50 years old and almost 75% of the building stock can be considered as energy inefficient. This issue is even more worrying when seeing that 75–90% of the existing buildings are expected to be standing by 2050. In order to address this emerging need for building increased energy efficiency the EU in the 2018 revision of the EPBD, aims to further promote smart building technologies, in particular through the establishment of a Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) for buildings⁵. The SRI aim to provide information on the technological readiness of buildings for interacting with their occupants and the energy grids, and their capabilities for more efficient operation and better performance through ICT technologies in the form of services. Therefore, the SRI should accelerate the transformation of the European Building Stock from standard and manually managed buildings to smart

buildings. Smart buildings integrate cutting edge ICT-based solutions for energy efficiency and energy flexibility for their daily operation. Such smart capabilities can effectively assist in creating healthier and more comfortable buildings with lower energy consumption and lower carbon footprint.

This digital transformation of the existing European building stock requires an ICT-based solution, which covers from the technological improvements of equipment until the business exploitation of the innovations born in this project. The overall framework presented in this paper aims to increase the smartness of existing buildings, covering all aspects of a building – from assets and their integration, to creation of knowledge, functions/services and business opportunities – all while keeping strict security and privacy levels. Overall, the mission is to provide an approach that changes the role of buildings from unorganised energy consumers to active agents orchestrating and optimising their energy consumption, production and storage, with the goal of increasing energy performance, maximising occupants’ benefit, and facilitating grid operation.

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ABBREVIATIONS

SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
EU	European Union
ICT	Information Communication Technologies
ESCO	Energy Service Company
HVAC	heating Ventilation Air Condition
DHW	domestic hot water

EMS	Energy Management System
IoT	Internet of things
NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interfaces- Linked Data
KG	Knowledge Graph
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
EVs	Electric Vehicles
PV	Photovoltaic
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
PMV	Predicted Mean Vote
PPD	Predicted Percentage Dissatisfied
IAQ	Indoor Air Quality
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
PM	Particle Material
VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
JRC	Joint Research Centre
DALY	Disability Adjusted Life Years
YOLL	Years of Life Lost
DSS	Decision Support System
CHP	Combined Heat Power
API	Application Programming Interface
EEB	Energy Efficiency Building
EPBD	Energy Performance Building Directive

REFERENCE

- [1]. European Commission, “Clean energy for all Europeans,” Luxembourg, 2019.

- [2]. European Commission, "Energy performance of buildings," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-performance-of-buildings>. [Accessed: 13-08-2019].
- [3]. Directive (eu) 2018/844 of the European parliament and of the council amending Directive 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings and Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency. Official Journal of the European Union L156, 2018, pp. 75–91.
- [4]. VITO, Waide Strategic Efficiency, OFFIS, and ECOFYS, "Support for setting up a Smart Readiness Indicator for buildings and related impact assessment," 2018.
- [5]. Final Report on the Technical Support to the Development of a Smart Readiness Indicator for Buildings, June 2020.
- [6]. <https://www.ashrae.org/technical-resources/resources>.
- [7]. Holopainen, R.; Tuomaala, P.; Hernandez, P.; Häkkinen, T.; Piira, K.; Piippo, J. Comfort assessment in the context of sustainable buildings: Comparison of simplified and detailed human thermal sensation methods. *Build. Environ.* 2014, 71, 60-70. doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2013.09.009.
- [8]. Paone and Bacher, The impact of building occupant behaviour on energy efficiency and methods to influence it: a review of the state of the art, *Energies* 2018, 11, 953; doi:10.3390/en11040953.
- [9]. Bert Brunekreef et al., "Air pollution and COVID-19", PE 658.216 - January 2021.
- [10]. <https://www.epa.gov/coronavirus/indoor-air-and-coronavirus-covid-19>.
- [11]. Agarwal et al., "Indoor air quality improvement in COVID-19 pandemic: Review", *Sustainable Cities and Society*, Volume 70, July 2021, 102942.
- [12]. <https://www.worldgbc.org/news-media/covid-19-brings-indoor-air-quality-monitoring-upfront>.
- [13]. Saini et al., "Indoor Air Quality Monitoring Systems and COVID-19", *Emerging Technologies During the Era of COVID-19 Pandemic*. 2021; 348: 133-147.
- [14]. Development of a Methodology to Include Multiple Benefits in Energy Efficiency Policy Development, European Commission JRC Technical Reports - draft study, 2019. <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC120683>.